

Walk the Yorke Trail

Help us develop a trail web map

We are developing a web map of the Walk the Yorke Trail and would love your help! This survey should take around 10 minutes to complete. Your answers will help us to shape the map to your needs.

This project has been approved by the University of South Australia's Human Research Ethics Committee. Please see the Participant Information Sheet attached on the last page. By completing and submitting the survey, you are indicating that you have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet and give your consent to be involved in the research.

About the Trail

The Walk the Yorke trail travels 500km around the Yorke Peninsula mainly following the coast. The trail showcases 'Yorokes', long beaches, spectacular sea cliffs, and rich farmland. The trail has routes for both walkers and cyclists and a wide variety of surfaces so that whether you prefer short walks on well formed tracks, day rides, or multi-day treks along rough bush paths there is something for you!

About the Project

You are probably familiar with Google Maps, and may be familiar with some of the trail specific online maps such as those found on Walking SA, Trails SA, and the Heysen Trail website. The aim of this project is to develop such an online map for the Walk the Yorke Trail. We intend to create a map that you can customise to your specific needs. This map will allow you to share information with other users, notify trail managers of issues, and for your safety register your trip intentions. We hope this map will prove useful and help you enjoy the trail!

We have put together a rough demonstration of the sort of map we hope to create. Our map will start by allowing you to tailor its appearance to your needs (walk, hike, bike, normal or large text etc.).

It will provide information on the various sections of the trail and allow you to submit information for the benefit of other trail users and to aid trail management. This demonstration is available at <https://joshgore.github.io/WalkTheYorke/> or by scanning the QR code.

Walk the Yorke

1. Where are you planning to travel along the Walk the Yorke this trip?

(mark and label with "n")

2. Where are you planning to travel along the Walk the Yorke this year?

(mark and label with "y")

Legend

Trail Type

- Beach Walk
- Walk
- Bike
- Shared Walk/Bike
- Trail Shelter

Roads

- Major Highway - Sealed
- Major Road - Sealed
- Secondary Road - Sealed
- Other Road - Sealed
- Other Road - Unsealed

- Camp Grounds
- Lighthouse
- Public Toilets
- Observation Point

Athorpe Islands

Your Trip Characteristics

1. How did you find out about the Walk the Yorke Trail?

2. How would you rate your personal knowledge about:

	Not Familiar				Very Familiar	
The Yorke Peninsula	1	2	3	4	5	
The Walk the Yorke Trail	1	2	3	4	5	

Thinking back to your most recent experience on the Walk the Yorke trail, please answer the following

3. Did you use a map to plan your trip? Yes / No

4. Do you have a paper-based map with you? Yes / No

5. Have you specifically downloaded a map? Yes / No

6 Did you visit any particular website to obtain information for this trip? Yes / No

If so, which site? _____

7. What was your main mode of travel?

Walking: Short Walk / Half Day / Full Day/ ____ Days

Cycling: How many kilometres are you planning on cycling today? _____

8. Who was walking/cycling with you?

Alone / Small Group (2-4) /Medium Group (5-10) / Large group (>10)

9. What was the primary benefit you desired from the Walk the Yorke experience?

Sport / Health / Social / Visit Nature / Other _____

Did you feel you attained this benefit? Yes / No

10. Please describe the group you travelled with

- | | |
|--|---------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Solo | <input type="checkbox"/> Friends |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Organised group | <input type="checkbox"/> Couple |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Family group | <input type="checkbox"/> School group |

11. How often do you visit the trail?

Weekly / Monthly / Yearly / Only once at this point

12. How far would you typically travel along the trail?

_____ km in _____ hrs / days

Your Satisfaction with the Walk the Yorke Trail

13. Please rate your level of agreement with the following statements

I think the access to drinking water along the trail was adequate

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

I thought the parking facilities were appropriate

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Your Background

14. How do you rate your own ability to use a topographic map?

Well Below Average Below Average Average Above Average Well above average

15. How familiar are you with the following?

Google Maps

Not at all familiar Slightly Familiar Somewhat Familiar Moderately Familiar Very Familiar

Google Earth

Not at all familiar Slightly Familiar Somewhat Familiar Moderately Familiar Very Familiar

Strava

Not at all familiar Slightly Familiar Somewhat Familiar Moderately Familiar Very Familiar

OpenStreetMap

Not at all familiar Slightly Familiar Somewhat Familiar Moderately Familiar Very Familiar

16. How often do you use the following when walking or cycling?

Paper Map

Never Almost Never Sometimes Almost Every Time Every Time

Outdoor GPS Device (e.g. Garmin eTrex)

Never Almost Never Sometimes Almost Every Time Every Time

Smartphone: Default Phone Maps (e.g. Google Maps)

Never Almost Never Sometimes Almost Every Time Every Time

Smartphone: Specific Walking/Cycling Map App(s)

Never Almost Never Sometimes Almost Every Time Every Time

Information about You

Postcode: _____ Gender: Male / Female Age: _____

Education Level

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Year 11 or below | <input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor degree |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Year 12 | <input type="checkbox"/> Postgraduate degree (Masters or higher) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Technical or trade qualification | <input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to say |

Lifestyle

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Young Single | <input type="checkbox"/> Middle family (youngest child 6 – 15 yrs) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Mature Single | <input type="checkbox"/> Mature Family |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Young Couple/No Children | <input type="checkbox"/> Older couple – no children at home |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Mature Couple/No Children | <input type="checkbox"/> Young family (youngest child <6 yrs) |

Would you be willing to participate in assessing the interactive map being developed for this walking trail? Yes / No

Would you like a one-page summary of the research findings emailed to you (this will occur in early December) Yes/ No

To facilitate this can you please neatly print your email below.

An interactive web map of the Walk the Yorke Trail

Participant Information Sheet

University of
South Australia

Division of IT, Engineering and Environment
School of Natural and Built Environments

Contact Information

If you have any questions or concerns about this research, please feel free to contact us:

Joshua Gore (gorja007@mymail.unisa.edu.au)

Dr Stefan Peters (stefan.peters@unisa.edu.au)

Assoc. Prof. Delene Weber (delene.weber@unisa.edu.au)

University of South Australia

Purpose of this Research

The University of South Australia is conducting this research project to gather information about current and potential users of the Walk the Yorke Trail. The results of this research will be used to create an interactive web map designed to aid users' enjoyment of the trail and improve trail management.

The data collected through this survey will be used in development of an interactive map. By completing and submitting the survey, you are indicating that you have read and understood this Participant Information Sheet and give your consent to be involved in this research. If you indicate your willingness to participate in a further study evaluating this map you will be sent an additional survey that will be approved by the human ethics committee.

You should be 18 years of age or older to participate in this survey. This project has been approved by the University of South Australia's Human Research Ethics Committee. If you have any ethical concerns about the project or questions about your rights as a participant please contact the Executive Officer of this Committee, Tel: +61 8 8302 3118; Email: Vicki.allen@unisa.edu.au

Project Funding

The Yorke Peninsula Council is assisting in the project by providing access to data, multimedia, and covering accommodation costs.

Risks and Benefits

It is not anticipated that there are any risks to participation in this study beyond those encountered during everyday life. A potential benefit for you is to have your preferences implemented on the finished trail map. By letting us know how you enjoy Walk the Yorke and your satisfaction with the trail you will also aid trail management.

Participation and Withdrawal

Your participation is entirely voluntary. You may withdraw from the study at any point, without consequences of any kind. If provided, identifying information will be removed from survey submissions by April 30th so survey submissions cannot be excluded after this point.

Data Collection, Storage and Use

This survey is being managed on a secure computer server. The responses you submit will be stored in a secure database that contains every response we receive (located in P2-28B, Mawson Lakes Campus of University of South Australia). Your responses will not be personally identifiable in this database. The data will be summarized and published in a report. The researcher will take every care to remove responses from any identifying material as early as possible. Likewise, individual responses will be kept confidential by the researcher and not be identified in the reporting of the research. Non-identifiable data will be retained for five years. Data collected online using the Survey Monkey platform will be downloaded and deleted as soon as collection has completed.

Reporting Findings

All records containing personal information will remain confidential and no information which could lead to identification of any individual will be released unless required by law. A summary of the research findings can be emailed to you at the completion of the study (expected date of completion is December 10, 2019) if you desire and you choose to provide an email address for this purpose.

Consent

By Submitting this survey, you agree to the following:

- I have read this Participant Information Sheet and the nature and purpose of the research project has been explained to me. I understand and agree to take part.
- I understand the purpose of the research project and my involvement in it.
- I understand that I may withdraw from the research project at any stage and that this will not affect my status now or in the future.
- I understand that while information gained during the study may be published, I will not be identified and my personal results will remain confidential, unless required by law.